

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHIBUYA****FIRST NAME: YUKIHIRO****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Word for Office 365 MSO

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1) INTRODUCTION

I have been working as an international development practitioner all through my career since 2003. Studying at Euclid University is a new endeavor not only in my professional career but also in my life as I will need to spend many hours for reading materials and writing. This is, in a sense, very challenging but also be an enjoyable journey as many new knowledge and skills will be following me at the end. My expectation of learning at Euclid University is to master theories and case studies by reviewing literatures, academic papers, books and video clips which are to be provided by the course. Another expectation is to equip skills to articulate my thoughts based on the theories and relevant cases so that I can better address practical issues which I confront day by day. In addition, these skills will also help me to write more convincing documents which can be read and referenced both by practitioners and scholars. Nowadays, it is becoming more and more common to change jobs between development agencies, academia, private company, non-profit organization and freelancer and I believe this general trend will continue in the coming decades as development agenda becomes more diverse and complicated. If I want to continue to be relevant in the industry, I need to keep changing and updating my knowledge and skills. In order to achieve these goals, for the first step, it is crucially important to learn academic writing rules, concept of plagiarism, style guide, etc. which period one of ACA-401 offers. The course pack comprehensively covers all the points which students should learn and equip to be a good academic writer. I found it valuable to start by reviewing this course pack at the beginning of the program.

2) HOW TO PERSUADE READERS IN ACADEMIC ESSAY?

I found that one of the most important messages in the course pack is “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). This statement seems to be very simple and obvious however it has fundamental importance in the entire study in this course. In particular, I have to keep in mind and need to understand through the upcoming study about what constitutes evidence and how we can use it as evidence in academic essays. As a practitioner, I have prepared many business documents. After reading the course pack, I found that the main differences between academic writing and business documents are that academic writing requires both “thesis statement (answer to question) and argument” (ibid.). In addition, it can also be said that “A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and writing” (EUCLID 2019, 2). On the other hand, business documents usually require problem statement and solutions to them. Since business documents normally purpose practical use and subsequent actions, the documents should provide clear messages and conclusions so that readers can subsequently come up with concrete actions. Business documents can refer to preceding academic papers as long as they can serve the purpose. Because of these fundamental differences between academic writing and business documents, it may take some time to change my mind set and gain skills to write proper academic writing. Having said that, since there are established rules and practice which have been widely shared by people all over the world, I believe I can gain the skills and knowledge as long as I learn using proper sources and follow proper methodology. In my view, the best way to write persuading academic essay is to write as many academic essays as possible, seek feedback from instructors and make the most of it and finally go back to the basic when facing difficulties in writing.

3) PLAGIARISM; WHAT ORIGINALITY MEANS?

I have worked for two international development institutions and both of them have very bureaucratic organizational culture. Under these bureaucratic cultures, originality sometimes hinders effective and efficient business processing and implementation. This is because staff in this kind of institutions share some kind of norms and implicit rules and they are supposed to follow them. Also, in business document preparation, originality is quite often not welcomed as bureaucratic organization does not like to make new precedence (originality) and instead, prefer to follow well accepted practices and ideas with some minor modifications and improvements. As course pack explains, “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Under the organizational culture I mentioned above, not many staff would pay attention to plagiarism as using similar ideas and even same sentences from other business documents are well accepted and common practices as long as it works well. On the other hand, when writing academic essays, “one of the most important things the writer should do is to avoid plagiarism” (ibid.), and I have to seriously keep this in mind all through my study in the course. I should understand that business

document which I prepared will be used under the name of the institution at the end therefore there are many review mechanisms before the document is finalized and released to the public however academic essay is to be developed under my name and own responsibility. When working at large scale institution, I sometime tend to forget that I'm protected by institution but I need to realize that academic essay, even if it is small one, is a produce of myself and it is only me who is responsible for what is written in the essay and I need to think of the importance of plagiarism from this perspective. Having said that, since I was not familiar with the concept of plagiarism, I was a bit too much worried how I can avoid plagiarism when write academic essays. After reading chapter two, I realized that as long as I properly give credit to the author "when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source" (ibid.), I do not need to worry too much. Rather, by making myself familiarize these basic rules, my academic essays could be differentiated from other essays which discuss similar topics. As a conclusion here, one of my findings is that understanding plagiarism could contribute to write effective academic essays with originality by properly applying information sources and differentiate what are known and what are my thoughts and findings.

4) STYLE MATTERS

By reading the course pack, I learnt that the definition of the style guide which is "A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (EUCLID 2019, 24). Although the institution where I'm currently working has its own style guide, I do not pay much attention to it as there are dedicated editorial unit and staff to take care of staff's writings. In addition, as a practitioner, it is critical to focus on actions and to solve problems rather than sticking to formalities therefore I have rarely paid much attention to it. Many creative writers, although from different reasons from mine, also believe "that the ability to follow standard English writing stale should be an innate quality for any writer" (ibid.). After reading chapter five, however, I realized it is important because it helps and "ensures that the writing style is consistent" (ibid.). If writing style is not consistent, obviously it is not considered worth reading in certain community. It will definitely take time to get used to certain style guide, but I believe CMS Crib Sheet will be the useful resources for me to come back when I have to check if I properly follow Chicago Style.

5) CONCLUSION

In the first period, I found a lot of new ideas and findings from the course pack. I believe learning this course pack at the beginning of the course will make a lot of difference in the subsequent learning in this entire program. In particular, this period is very useful to make a bridge between business writing and academic writing. Obviously, just reading the course pack will not be sufficient to fully equip the rules and ideas and more practice will need to be followed through the upcoming periods. It does make sense to learn this topic first and it is relevant not only to the entire program but also entire lifelong learning after finishing the program in Euclid University. This period is a foundation of the academic

writing and I will need to come back to the course pack time to time to check if my understanding is correct.

REFERENCES

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